

NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM SECTOR

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Abstract

Today, it is fair to say that the world belongs to technology. Big data, data warehouses, networks, the internet, artificial intelligence, robots - these are not " the distant future ", but the things we already use every day. New technologies based on artificial intelligence are widely used in all areas of human and professional activity, improving the quality of work and life. This article provides a brief overview of new intelligent technologies that are being implemented, quite successfully, in the tourism sector.

Key words: *information technologies, artificial intelligence, tourism.*

JEL: *F61, F62, F63, M31*

Information technologies are constantly developing being successfully and easily introduced into our daily lives. Technologies today, in their development, have reached a very high level, and have started to use artificial intelligence.

A person's mental intelligence is a set of accumulated knowledge, the ability to properly apply it, the ability to find logical solutions [1]. Most scientific sources define artificial intelligence as systems that can mimic human functions to perform certain tasks; systems that can learn from available data.

Artificial intelligence is a rapidly developing field of computer science. Artificial intelligence-based systems can process and analyze huge amounts of data accumulated by travel companies, make predictions (booking tickets, hotels; setting prices), segment customers (to identify traveler preferences) and solve other complex tasks.

The indisputable advantages of intelligent systems are: (1) large amounts of data storage; (2) high speed, performance and efficiency of data processing; (3) unbiased problem solving or decision making (lack of emotionality); (4) expertise/experience; (5) presence of multiple options for problem solving; (6) user friendliness for customers (clear and friendly interfaces).

In everyday life and in the professional domain, artificial intelligence comes in the form of machines or information technology. Artificial intelligence is widely used in all areas of human activity and helps to facilitate and automate the performance of many tasks. Even the tourism sector has not remained far from modern intellectual progress. The tourism industry is one of the most developed sectors of the economy, including passenger transport, hotel business, restaurants, entertainment and cultural events, etc.

Let's get acquainted with the new intelligent technologies that are already used in the tourism industry [2; 3; 4, 5, 6, 7]:

- Biometric identification - used to improve the quality of service at the airport, in hotels, at events of different types.
- Chatbots based on artificial intelligence - these are online assistants, voice assistants; used to communicate with customers, to provide personalized support in choosing a tourism product.
- Robot waiters are artificial intelligence machines deployed in restaurants/cafes to serve customers.

- Concierge robots - these machines are installed in hotels and business centers; these machines perform the following tasks: identifying visitors, scanning passports, issuing badges, etc. The robots are integrated with the building access system.

- Robots in hotels to provide guest services: cleaning, disinfecting the air, providing necessary information, etc.

- Artificial intelligence-based information systems in tourism allow: analysis of customer behavioral data and, accordingly, the formulation of a personalized offer; prediction of air ticket prices based on collected system data; search for profitable flight options (Aviasales); travel planning and search (Rome2rio).

- Online booking of tours are services where guides can showcase any city in the world (<https://www.sputnik8.com/>).

- Travel navigators - allow route planning.

The use of the latest smart technologies in the tourism sector will help cut some of the company's costs, increase customer satisfaction, improve the quality of customer service and enhance the attractiveness of the service.

Conclusion:

The use of artificial intelligence-based systems for processing and analyzing big data will allow: extracting valuable information (knowledge) when processing large amounts of data for management; more accurate forecasting (prices, bookings); development of customized tourism products; development of new products and services; better decision making for a successful business; for companies to be competitive in the market.

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